

The Climate-Energy Security Tri-Lemma in Vanuatu: Securing a Resilient and Renewable Grid Against Intensifying Cyclones

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ABSTRACT

The challenge Vanuatu faces is a tough one, that is to meet the criteria of energy security, sustainability, and climate change resilience all at once. These three are interrelated; a problem in one area will make the other two worse. They require intelligent, incremental solutions that can benefit all three simultaneously. Lack of enforcement of refrigerator standards affects food security and health.

Vanuatu's development is challenged by its highly import-dependent, fossil fuel-based economy, its ambitious target of converting to 100% renewable power by 2030, and an energy system that is extremely sensitive to the increasingly intense tropical. Vanuatu's development is challenged by its highly import-dependent, fossil fuel-based economy, its ambitious target of converting to 100% renewable power by 2030, and an energy system that is extremely sensitive to the increasingly intense tropical cyclones.

The paper explores how Vanuatu can manage its “climate energy-security dilemma,” or the challenge of balancing energy security, sustainability, and climate change. It contends that in order to manage this dilemma, energy efficiency and the use of renewables must be viewed through the lens of national security strategy, rather than simply a technical fix.

Using a critical analysis of the most important energy policy instruments in Vanuatu namely the National Energy Road Map (NERM) and National Energy Efficiency Strategy and Action Plan (NEESAP), and the nascent Vanuatu Carbon Cooperation Framework 2025, this paper illustrates how demand management lower costs, improve cyclone resistance, and international finance can secure a sustainable energy future.

1. Introduction

Vanuatu, a Pacific Small Island Developing State (SID) with a population of approximately 300,000, stands at the forefront of multiple global crises.¹ It faces a profound "climate-energy security tri-lemma," a term describing the immense challenge of simultaneously achieving and balancing three critical objectives: energy security, environmental sustainability, and climate resilience.² The nation's development is constrained by its heavy reliance on imported fossil fuels, a vulnerability quantified by the National Energy Road Map (NERM), which notes that Vanuatu "ranks among the nations with the very highest petroleum energy intensity."³ Concurrently, its sovereign ambition to transition to 100% renewable energy generation by 2030 is being besieged by escalating climate impacts, particularly the intensification of tropical cyclones.⁴ Crucially, achieving these goals is hampered by a "severe lack of means of implementation," with the nation's climate commitments being "fully conditional, and based on the availability of external finance."⁵

This paper argues that for Vanuatu, to meet rising demand while keeping electricity systems affordable, energy security in an era of climate change necessitates a grid that is simultaneously renewable, resilient, and financed through

innovative mechanisms. Through an integrated analysis of national policy, the NERM, the National Energy Efficiency Strategy and Action Plan (NEESAP), and the Carbon Cooperation Framework 2025, this paper posits that a strategic synthesis of energy efficiency including digital system management, develop integrated decentralized resilience energy systems, and Article 6 carbon finance to scale grids, storage and flexibility solutions to manage variable renewables and new demand profiles, is essential for navigating this trilemma and securing a sovereign, sustainable future⁶ informed by scholarship on integrated climate-smart development.

2. Energy Vulnerability Trilemma in Vanuatu

The core problem for Vanuatu is that its energy system is vulnerable on all three fronts of the trilemma. First, energy security is compromised by a near-total dependence on imported petroleum products.⁷ This dependency makes electricity expensive and unreliable, hindering economic growth. This vulnerability is compounded by what the NEESAP identifies as an "uncontrollable influx of inefficient and low-priced appliances," which increases overall electricity demand and locks in higher operational costs.⁸ The NEESAP reveals that the current regulatory Framework, the Energy Efficiency

¹ Government of Vanuatu Ministry of Climate Change, "National Energy Efficiency Strategy and Action Plan (2022 - 2030)." November 2022, 9, <https://doe.gov.vu/index.php/news-events/news/155-vanuatu-validates-national-energy-efficiency-strategy-and-action-plan>.

² Bazilian, Morgan, et al., R. K. Pachauri, and L. Meyer, "The Energy Security Nexus and the Energy Trilemma," London: *Global Energy Challenge: Environment, Development and Security*, World Scientific (2015): 58.

³ Government of Vanuatu Department of Energy, "Updated National Energy Road Map 2016-2030. Government of Vanuatu," May 2016, 21, chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://doe.gov.vu/images/docs/publications/Implementation_Plan.pdf.

⁴ Catherine Wade et al, "Decentralized Renewable Energy and the Energy Trilemma in Small Island Developing States," *Energy Policy* 162, no. 112783 (March 2022): 3.

⁵ Christopher Bartlett, "Vanuatu National Carbon Cooperation Framework," Government of Vanuatu Ministry of Climate Change, 2025, 6.

Kathryn J. Bowen et al., *Lessons in Climate Smart Policies: A Framework for Integrated Low Carbon Resilient Development* (Gland, Switzerland: WWF and ODI, 2019), 12, https://d2ouvy59podg6k.cloudfront.net/downloads/lessons_in_climate_smart_policies__a_framework_for_integrated_low_carbon_resilient_deve.pdf.

⁷ Government of Vanuatu Department of Energy, "Updated National Energy Road Map 2016-2030. Government of Vanuatu," 21.

⁸ Government of Vanuatu Ministry of Climate Change, "National Energy Efficiency Strategy and Action Plan (2022 - 2030)," 9.

of Electrical Appliances, Equipment and Lighting Products Act (No. 24 of 2016), covers only six product categories namely: Refrigerators and Freezers; Air Conditioners; Incandescent Lamps (light bulbs); Compact Fluorescent Lamps (CFLs); Linear Fluorescent Lamps (LFLs) and Ballasts (for fluorescent lighting), leaving high-growth appliances like televisions, computers, and washing machines unregulated, thereby perpetuating energy insecurity.⁹

The consequences of this regulatory gap are measurable and significant. The influx of inefficient, non-compliant appliances acts as a hidden tax on Vanuatu's economy, increasing national energy demand and requiring expensive diesel imports to meet baseload power. This creates a perverse cycle: higher fuel costs make electricity more expensive for consumers and the government, which in turn reduces capital available for investments in renewable energy generation and grid hardening. Furthermore, the absence of standards for products like refrigeration directly impacts food security and public health - key components of societal resilience during and after climate disasters when supply chains are disrupted. Closing this regulatory gap is therefore not merely a technical market correction but a foundational step toward energy sovereignty.¹⁰

Second, the pursuit of environmental sustainability is a key national priority; however, progress has been slower than anticipated, mainly due to financial constraints. The NERM

acknowledges barriers, including the high cost of new renewable capacity.¹¹ The Carbon Cooperation Framework identifies international carbon markets as a vital source of "new and additional climate finance" to close this gap, noting that Vanuatu's Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC)¹² mitigation targets are conditional upon such support.¹³ Critically, the NEESAP provides a pathway to overcome this, stating that "energy efficiency investments can in many cases be more cost-effective than investing in new renewable energy generation capacity."¹⁴ The strategy formalizes this by targeting 15% savings in the energy sector, equivalent to a reduction of 30 ktCO₂e per year, directly supporting Vanuatu's Revised NDC.¹⁵ This represents a strategic pivot to treating avoided demand as a primary energy resource and a potential source of verifiable emissions reductions for carbon cooperation.

Third, and most critically, the climate resilience of the entire energy infrastructure is severely threatened. The effects of Cyclone Pam in 2015 "reiterated Vanuatu's vulnerability to natural hazards... and the importance of developing resilient infrastructure and energy supply chains."¹⁶ A centralized grid with extensive above-ground transmission lines is highly susceptible to damage, leading to prolonged blackouts. This creates a vicious cycle: a fragile grid undermines the nation's ability to respond to the very climate disasters that are

⁹ Ibid., 12.

¹⁰ Diana Urge-Vorsatz et al., "Measuring the Co-Benefits of Climate Change Mitigation," *Annual Review of Environment and Resources* 39 (October 2014): 549.

¹¹ Government of Vanuatu Department of Energy, "Updated National Energy Road Map 2016-2030. Government of Vanuatu," 34.

¹² A Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) is a climate action plan submitted by each country under the Paris Agreement, outlining its commitments to reduce national emissions and adapt to climate impacts. Vanuatu's Revised NDC includes a conditional target of 100% renewable

energy in electricity generation by 2030. See *Vanuatu National Carbon Cooperation Framework*, 10.

¹³ Christopher Bartlett, "Vanuatu National Carbon Cooperation Framework," 10.

¹⁴ Government of Vanuatu Ministry of Climate Change, "National Energy Efficiency Strategy and Action Plan (2022 - 2030)," 9.

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Government of Vanuatu Department of Energy, "Updated National Energy Road Map 2016-2030. Government of Vanuatu," 26.

becoming more frequent and severe.¹⁷ As scholarship on resilient energy systems underscores, resilience requires "redundancy, diversity, and decentralization"—qualities that are inadequate in Vanuatu's current model.¹⁸

3. History/ Context Information

The Vanuatu government recognized these interconnected challenges and formulated a comprehensive policy response in the National Energy Road Map (NERM), first endorsed in 2013 and updated in 2016. The NERM's vision to "energize Vanuatu's growth and development through the provision of secure, affordable, widely accessible, high-quality, clean energy services" demonstrates an integrated understanding of the problem.¹⁹

The NEESAP 2022-2030, developed with support from the Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI) a key partner in developing the Carbon Cooperation Framework is the critical next step. It was designed to "add value and complement the NERM 2016" by providing the missing cohesive strategic guidance for energy efficiency.²⁰ It is an eight-year plan built on a Theory of Change (TOC) framework with 12 detailed objectives.²¹ The plan's comprehensive nature ranging from strengthening appliance standards to promoting green buildings reflects the understanding that energy efficiency is "distributed across the institutional, commercial

establishments, homes, appliances, businesses, and vehicles," requiring a whole-of-economy approach.²²

a) The Role of the National Green Energy Fund (NGEF) as a Precursor Model

A critical, though underutilized, component of Vanuatu's policy landscape is the National Green Energy Fund (NGEF). Established as part of the NERM architecture, the NGEF was designed to mobilize domestic and external finance for sustainable energy projects. Its prioritization criteria which include gender impact, rural focus, benefits for vulnerable populations, and potential for scale prefigure the holistic, sustainable development approach later codified in the Carbon Cooperation Framework's safeguards. However, as noted in the NERM Implementation Plan/ Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) plan²³ past difficulties in accessing consistent funding have limited the NGEF's impact.

The new Carbon Cooperation Framework can be viewed as an evolution of this model, scaling it from a domestic project fund to an international mechanism capable of generating significantly larger revenue streams through the commoditization of verified mitigation outcomes. This transition from grant-dependent fund to market-based financial mechanism represents first a crucial maturation in Vanuatu's climate finance strategy and second a strategic move to diversify finance away from traditional, and often

¹⁷ Samuel Fankhauser and Thomas K. J. McDermott, "Understanding the Adaptation Gap: Why Are Some Countries Adapting More Than Others?" *Climate Policy* 16, no. 4 (2016): 440.

¹⁸ Benjamin K. Sovacool, "The Importance of Flexibility and Resilience in Securing a Sustainable Energy Future," *Energy Policy* 37, no. 12 (December 2009): 5490.

¹⁹ Government of Vanuatu Department of Energy, "Updated National Energy Road Map 2016-2030. Government of Vanuatu," 8.

²⁰ Government of Vanuatu Ministry of Climate Change, "National Energy Efficiency Strategy and Action Plan (2022 - 2030)," 7.

²¹ *Ibid.*, 13–22.

²² *Ibid.*, 11.

²³ Measurement, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) refers to a multi-step process for quantifying greenhouse gas emission reductions and tracking climate action. Robust MRV is essential for ensuring the integrity of carbon credits and tracking progress against the NERM and NDC targets. See Government of Vanuatu Department of Energy, "Updated National Energy Road Map 2016-2030 Implementation Plan" (July 2019), 58.

unpredictable, aid dependencies, creating a more sovereign revenue stream for national priorities.²⁴

b) The 2025 Vanuatu Carbon Cooperation Framework

The 2025 Vanuatu Carbon Cooperation Framework now provides the financial architecture to implement these plans.²⁵ It establishes the governance and systems to "mobilise new and additional climate finance through carbon cooperation, technology and capacity, as a means to support Vanuatu's long-term decarbonisation and resilient development."²⁶ The Framework explicitly lists "Renewable Energy Capacity Addition" and "Energy Efficient Building (Green Building)" as priority sectors eligible for carbon cooperation, directly linking NEESAP objectives to potential international finance under Article 6²⁷ of the Paris Agreement and voluntary carbon markets.²⁸ This approach aligns with the integrated climate-smart development framework, which advocates for policies that simultaneously reduce emissions, manage climate-related risks, and support sustainable development.²⁹

4. Proposition and recommendations

While the NERM, NEESAP, and the Carbon Cooperation Framework provide a strong strategic foundation, their implementation must be accelerated and strategically aligned

to achieve their objectives. The following recommendations are proposed, leveraging the actionable frameworks of the NEESAP and the new Carbon Cooperation Framework:

a) Execute the NEESAP's Decentralization and Demand-Reduction Agenda as a Carbon Cooperation Priority

The government and donors should aggressively fund and implement NEESAP objectives that inherently promote resilient development. Objective 7, the complete phase-out of incandescent lamps and Compact Fluorescent Lamps (CFLs), is a prime example. The strategy aims for 100% of households and commercial centers to use Light Emitting Diodes (LEDs) by 2030, which will reduce peak demand on a fragile grid.³⁰ The resulting emission reductions should be packaged and authorized under the Framework as Mitigation Outcomes (MOs), generating revenue through the Vanuatu Carbon Registry (VCR) to fund further efficiency programs.³¹ This operationalizes the principle that carbon finance should support conditional NDC targets and creates a self-reinforcing cycle of investment.³²

²⁴ Carola Betzold, "Fueling the Pacific: Aid for Renewable Energy Across Pacific Island Countries," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 82, no. 3 (February 2018): 3435.

²⁵ Christopher Bartlett, "Vanuatu National Carbon Cooperation Framework," 1.

²⁶ *Ibid.*, 22.

²⁷ Article 6.2 of the Paris Agreement enables cooperative approaches between countries for transferring mitigation outcomes. It allows a country like Vanuatu to authorize the export of emission reductions to another country, which can use them toward its climate target, provided a "corresponding adjustment" is made to avoid double-counting. See Government of Vanuatu, *Vanuatu National Carbon Cooperation Framework* (Port Vila, 2025), 31. A corresponding adjustment is an accounting mechanism under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement. When a

mitigation outcome (like an ITMO) is transferred internationally, the host country must add an equivalent amount of emissions to its national inventory, and the acquiring country subtracts it, ensuring the emission reduction is counted only once toward global goals. See *Vanuatu National Carbon Cooperation Framework*, 33.

²⁸ Christopher Bartlett, "Vanuatu National Carbon Cooperation Framework," 40.

²⁹ WWF, *Lessons in Climate Smart Policies: A Framework for Integrated Low Carbon Resilient Development*, 22.

³⁰ Government of Vanuatu Ministry of Climate Change, "National Energy Efficiency Strategy and Action Plan (2022 - 2030)," 39.

³¹ Christopher Bartlett, "Vanuatu National Carbon Cooperation Framework," 33-35.

³² *Ibid.*, 10.

b) Mandate Climate Resilience Standards via Green Building Codes Financed by Carbon Revenue

The NERM's call for resilient infrastructure must be operationalized through NEESAP's Objective 12, which mandates the "development and introduction of Energy Conservation Building Codes (ECBC)."³³ and "Green Building guidelines."³⁴ Donor funding and a share of proceeds from carbon credit sales, as outlined in the Framework's benefit-sharing mechanisms, should be directed towards ensuring all new public and commercial buildings meet these verified resilience and efficiency criteria.³⁵ Directly link climate finance to physical climate resilience, ensuring new assets are both low-carbon and durable.

c) Build Regulatory and Testing Capacity Using Carbon Market Proceeds

The "uncontrollable influx" of inefficient appliances is a critical security threat.³⁶ NEESAP Objectives 1-4 provide the remedy: expanding the list of regulated products from six to twenty-five, adopting robust Minimum Energy Performance Standards

(MEPS)³⁷, and establishing a third-party testing laboratory.³⁸ The Framework allows for fees and a "share of proceeds" from carbon transactions to be directed to regulatory bodies.³⁹ These funds should be prioritized to empower the Department of Energy to secure the appliance supply chain, creating a sustainable funding model for enforcing energy sovereignty.

d) Leverage Carbon Markets to De-Risk and Accelerate Renewable Investments

The Framework's provisions for Article 6.2 (bilateral transfers) and Article 6.4 (centralized mechanism) should be strategically used to attract investment in the NERM's flagship goal of 100% renewable electricity.⁴⁰ By authorizing Internationally Transferred Mitigation Outcomes (ITMOs)⁴¹ from new solar, wind, or biomass projects, Vanuatu can create a new revenue stream that improves the business case for renewables, directly addressing the high upfront costs identified in the NERM.⁴² This aligns with the post-UNFCCC COP30 imperative to scale up predictable finance for just energy transitions in vulnerable nations.⁴³

³³ Energy Conservation Building Codes (ECBC) are regulations that set minimum requirements for the energy-efficient design and construction of new buildings or significant renovations. Their development and enforcement under NEESAP Objective 12 are critical for reducing long-term energy demand and enhancing climate resilience. See *Vanuatu NEESAP*, 46.

³⁴ Government of Vanuatu Ministry of Climate Change, "National Energy Efficiency Strategy and Action Plan (2022 - 2030)," 46.

³⁵ Christopher Bartlett, "Vanuatu National Carbon Cooperation Framework," 89-90.

³⁶ Government of Vanuatu Ministry of Climate Change, "National Energy Efficiency Strategy and Action Plan (2022 - 2030)," 9.

³⁷ Minimum Energy Performance Standards (MEPS) are regulatory specifications that define the minimum level of energy efficiency that an appliance or product must meet to be legally sold in a market. Expanding MEPS is a core objective of Vanuatu's NEESAP to combat the influx of inefficient appliances. See Government of Vanuatu, "National Energy Efficiency Strategy and Action Plan (NEESAP) 2022-2030*" (Port Vila, 2022), 29.

³⁸ Government of Vanuatu Ministry of Climate Change, "National Energy Efficiency Strategy and Action Plan (2022 - 2030)," 29-32.

³⁹ Christopher Bartlett, "Vanuatu National Carbon Cooperation Framework," 89-90.

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*, 31-37.

⁴¹ Internationally Transferred Mitigation Outcomes (ITMOs) are units representing greenhouse gas emission reductions or removals that are authorized by a host country (e.g., Vanuatu) for transfer to another country to meet its Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC). The transfer requires a corresponding adjustment in the national greenhouse gas inventories of both countries. See *Vanuatu National Carbon Cooperation Framework*, 31-32.

⁴² Michaelowa et al Axel, "The Future of Carbon Markets: Post-Paris and Beyond," *Climate Policy* 19, no. 3 (2019): 295

⁴³ UNFCCC, *Conference of the Parties Serving as the Meeting of the Parties to the Paris Agreement, Fifth Session (COP30), Decision -/CMA.5. Para. 15.* (Belém, Brazil: UNFCCC, 2025).

e) Implement a Provincial Piloting Program for Integrated Resilience

To embody the principles of integrated, low-carbon, resilient development, Vanuatu should launch a targeted, province-level pilot program that bundles multiple recommendations into an integrated resilience package. For example, on Tanna or Ambrym, the government could:⁴⁴

- a) Deploy a Decentralized Renewable Micro-grid: Fund solar PV and battery storage systems to serve cluster of villages especially schools, places of worship, health centres and home community level.
- b) Conduct a Coordinated Appliance Replacement Scheme: Simultaneously roll out a program to replace inefficient, high-wattage appliances (e.g., old refrigerators, incandescent bulbs) with highly efficient digital systems certified under the expanded NEESAP standards, directly lowering the micro-grid's demand and size requirements.
- c) Apply the Carbon Cooperation Framework: Measure the emissions avoided by the renewable micro-grid and the efficient appliances. Package these as a single bundle of ITMOs for sale through the VCR. The revenue generated would be legally mandated to flow back into a community-managed trust fund to scale grids, ongoing micro-grid maintenance and accelerated deployment of utility-scale batteries and other flexible solutions to meet renewable and new demand profiles and resilience projects.

This pilot would serve multiple strategic purposes. Operationally, it creates a tangible model of a resilient, low-

carbon energy system. Financially, it tests the 'bankability' of integrated mitigation activities under the new Framework. Politically, it delivers visible co-benefits reliable power, lower household energy costs, local revenue building crucial public support for the national tri-lemma strategy.

A decentralized micro-grid pilot directly addresses the core finding of contemporary SIDS energy research: that resolving the trilemma requires moving away from vulnerable centralized systems toward resilient, distributed generation.⁴⁵ Success would provide a replicable blueprint for other islands and strengthen Vanuatu's position when negotiating results-based climate finance with bilateral and multilateral partners. This pilot, by prioritizing community-managed benefits and equitable access to resilient power, would reframe the energy transition as a matter of justice and ethical development, ensuring the most vulnerable populations are not left behind.⁴⁶

5. Conclusion

Vanuatu's climate-energy security trilemma presents a formidable but not insurmountable challenge. The path forward requires recognizing that the NERM provides the destination, the NEESAP offers the detailed vehicle for the journey, and the Carbon Cooperation Framework supplies the essential fuel. The failure of any one component stalls the entire enterprise. Therefore, the most urgent task is not further policy design, but the dedicated resourcing and political commitment to integrated execution. This includes staffing the new Carbon Unit within the Department of Climate Change, finalizing the methodologies for the Vanuatu Carbon Registry, and initiating the capacity-building programs for

⁴⁴ Bowen et al., *Lessons in Climate Smart Policies: A Framework for Integrated Low Carbon Resilient Development*, 22.

⁴⁵ Wade et al., "Decentralised Renewable Energy and the Energy Trilemma in Small Island Developing States," 3.

⁴⁶ Benjamin K. Sovacool et al., "Energy Decisions Reframed as Justice and Ethical Concerns," *Nature Energy* 1, no. 5 (May 2016): 16024.

provincial governments and customary landowners outlined in the Framework. The proposed integrated provincial pilots offer a pragmatic starting point to demonstrate feasibility, build institutional muscle memory, and generate early wins that can attract larger-scale investment.

The National Energy Road Map 2016-2030 and the National Energy Efficiency Strategy and Action Plan 2022-2030 demonstrate a sophisticated understanding that the goals of energy security, sustainability, and resilience are deeply intertwined. The *Vanuatu Carbon Cooperation Framework 2025* now provides the critical financial and governance architecture to operationalize this understanding. By treating energy efficiency and renewable energy not just as technical goals but as bankable mitigation activities and by rigorously implementing the linked strategies of appliance standards, building codes, and carbon finance Vanuatu can build a more resilient, renewable, and efficient energy system. The successful execution of this integrated policy suite is essential to moving beyond a fragile grid that is a liability during disasters, towards a robust network that serves as the backbone for climate adaptation, economic development, and a secure future for all ni-Vanuatu.

6. Conflict of Interest

The author states that there is no conflict of interest.

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